

New data on the Palaearctic Xantholinini.
12. New species, new designations and new records
(Coleoptera: Staphylinidae)
275th contribution to the knowledge of the Staphylinidae

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Abstract. Species of Xantholinini from the Palaearctic Region are listed. Some of these are common but the records expand the known distribution of the taxa; other species are less common and new records for the named countries are given: *Gauropterus bucharicus* Bernhauer, 1905 (Turkmenistan), *Nudobius umbratus* (Motschulsky, 1869) (Czechia), *Gyrophypnus ochripennis* (Eppelsheim, 1892) (Central Russia), *Xantholinus elegans* (Olivier, 1795) (Aosta Valley, Italy), *Xantholinus gridellii* Coiffait, 1956 (Jordan), and *Phacophallus flavipennis* (Kraatz, 1859) (Pakistan: see Distribution of the species); lectotype and paralectotypes are designated for *Xantholinus laniger* Fauvel, 1899. A new species (*Xantholinus chalusianus* sp. n.) from Iran is described and figured. Furthermore the following nomenclature act is made: *Xantholinus postfactus* nom. nov. for *X. apterus* Bordoni, 2016, nom. preocc. by *X. apterus* Bernhauer, 1939.

Riassunto. Nuovi dati sugli Xantholinini paleartici. 12. Nuova specie, nuove designazioni e nuovi dati geonemici (Coleoptera, Staphylinidae). 275° contributo alla conoscenza degli Staphylinidae. Vengono elencati Xantholinini della Regione Paleartica. Alcune specie sono comuni, ma i nuovi dati geonemici ampliano la loro distribuzione; altre sono meno comuni e risultano nuove per le regioni citate: *Gauropterus bucharicus* Bernhauer, 1905 (Turkmenistan), *Nudobius umbratus* (Motschulsky, 1869) (Repubblica Ceca), *Gyrophypnus ochripennis* (Eppelsheim, 1892) (Russia Centrale), *Xantholinus elegans* (Olivier, 1795) (Valle d'Aosta), *Xantholinus gridellii* Coiffait, 1956 (Giordania) e *Phacophallus flavipennis* (Kraatz, 1859) (Pakistan: cfr Distribuzione della specie). L'autore designa lectotipo e paralectotipi per *Xantholinus laniger* Fauvel, 1899 e descrive ed illustra *Xantholinus chalusianus* sp. n. dell'Iran. Inoltre viene effettuato il seguente atto nomenclaturale: *Xantholinus postfactus* nom. nov. per *X. apterus* Bordoni, 2016, nom. preocc. da *X. apterus* Bernhauer, 1939.

Key words. Coleoptera, Staphylinidae, Xantholinini, geonemical data, new records, new species, lectotype, Europe, Central Asia.

Introduction

Among the Xantholinini from the Palaearctic Region received in study in different times from several institutions and private collections, I found some interesting species deserving of mention. Some of these are common but the new records increase or confirm the known distribution of the taxa; other species are less common and the records are new for numerous countries. In this short note, I show the result of this study.

Acronyms

cB coll. Bordoni, Firenze, Italy
cC coll. Canepari, S. Donato Milanese, Italy
cH coll. Hayashi, Kawanishi, Japan
cI coll. Ito, Kyoto, Japan

IRSNB	Institut royal des Sciences naturelles, Bruxelles, Belgium
ISBD	Institute of Systematic Biology, Daugavpils, Latvia
MCSNG	Museo civico di Storia naturale, Genova, Italy
MM	Manchester Museum, Manchester, England
NHMB	Naturhistorisches Museum, Basel, Switzerland

Taxonomy

Gauropterus sanguinipennis (Kolenati, 1846)

Examined material. Iran, Bujnurd Umg., Moh. Reza Shah, C. Blumenthal 18.VI.1974, 1 ex. (NHMB), 1 ex. (cB).

Distribution. Rhodes, Greece, Turkey, Caucasus, Iran, Armenia (SMETANA, 2004; BORDONI, 2005).

Gauropterus sanguinipes (Reitter, 1889)

Examined material. Kavkaz, Abhazski range, Dombai vill., leg. ? 25.VII.1994, 1 ex. (cI), 1 ex. (cB).

Distribution. Cyprus, Turkey, Caucasus, Iran, Azerbaijan (SMETANA, 2004; BORDONI, 2005).

Gauropterus bucharicus Bernhauer, 1905

Examined material. Turkmenistan, Kuhitang (Mts), Daraj-Dere valley, 900 m, V. Dolin 4.V.1996, 1 ex. (cH), 1 ex. (cB).

Distribution. The species is known from Afghanistan and Uzbekistan (SMETANA, 2004; BORDONI, 2005). New record for Turkmenistan.

Gauropterus fulgidus (Fabricius, 1787)

Examined material. Syria, Jable, J. Macek 10.X.1988, 1 ex. (NHMB); Morocco, Chaouia-Ouardigha prov., El Borouj vic., O. Oum er Rbia riv., A. Anichtchenko 14-15.VI.2010, 2 exx. (ISBD), 1 ex. (cB); Italy, Liguria, Ventimiglia, leg. ? 4.IX.1960, 1 ex. (MCSNG); Deiva Marina, torr. Deiva, leg. ? 11.VII.1987, 1 ex. (MCSNG); Sardinia, Buroli Cannas (CA), 200 m, leg. ? 20.VI.1985, 1 ex. (MCSNG); Tunisia, Is. Djerba, El Menzel, leg. ? 17-23.IX.1975, 1 ex. (MCSNG).

Distribution. Widespread species in Europe and Mediterranean area (SMETANA, 2004).

Nudobius fasciatus (Hochhuth, 1849)

Examined material. Iran, Mazandaran to Chorti (SW Chalkorudi), 1260 m, G. Sama 21.VI-3.VII.2003, 1 ex. (cC), 1 ex. (cB).

Distribution. Azerbaijan, Iran (SMETANA, 2004). This record confirms the presence of this species in Iran.

Note. In another contribution (BORDONI, 2010) I have referred the species (olim *Calontholinus* Reitter, 1908) to the genus *Nudobius* Thomson, 1860 for the external characters and genitalia.

Nudobius umbratus (Motschulsky, 1860)

Examined material. Czech Rep., Moravia merid., Ostrovacice, P. Cechovsky 10.III.1995, 1 ♂ (cC), 1 ♂ (cB); Kavkaz, Abhazski range, Teberda, leg. ? 14.VII.1994, 2 exx. (cI), 1 ex. (cB).

Distribution. The species is known from Armenia, Georgia, South Russia, South Ukraine (SMETANA, 2004). New record for Czechia.

Gyrophynus ochripennis (Eppelsheim, 1892)

Examined material. C Russia, Tyer reg., Neligovo vill., leg. ? 5.VI.1995, 1 ♂ (cB).

Distribution. South Russia (Kavkaz), Central Asia (SMETANA, 2004). New record for Central Russia.

Xantholinus rufipennis Erichson, 1839

Examined material. Kreta, Chora Sfakion, 100-300 m, W. Wittmer 20.IV.1971, 1 ex. (NHMB); Syria, Djebel Anzarjiya, Al Tamaza, 699 m, J. Macek 7.V.1989, 1 ex. (NHMB), 1 ex. (cB).

Distribution. East Europe and East Mediterranean (SMETANA, 2004).

Xantholinus puthzi Bordoni, 1979

Examined material. Turkey, Antalya, 36 km N, W. Wittmer 4.V.1969, 1 ♂ (cB).

Distribution. Turkey (SMETANA, 2004).

***Xantholinus chalusianus* sp. n.**

Examined material. Holotype, ♂: Iran, Chalus, Wittmer & Bothmer 28-29.IV.1970 (NHMB).

Description. Body (Fig. 1) length: 9.5 mm; from anterior margin of head to posterior margin of elytra: 5 mm. Head reddish amaranth, pronotum reddish brown, elytra orange, abdomen brown dark; posterior margin of 5-6 visible segments and genital segment yellowish; antennae and legs brown. Head sub-ovoidal, narrow forward, with rounded sides from the eyes to the neck. Eyes small and flat. Surface of head with numerous, deep, fine punctures. Pronotum sub-rectangular, a little longer and narrower than head, with slightly oblique anterior margins and sinuate sides. Surface with numerous, deep, dense punctation, apart a median band, in which irregular distal series of 14-15 punctures and irregular lateral series of 11-12 punctures can be hardly distinguished. Elytra large, longer and wider than pronotum, a little dilated posteriad, with rounded humeral angles. Surface with numerous, very fine punctures, arranged in numerous series. Abdomen with traces of more or less transverse microstriature and fine punctation on the sides.

Tergite and sternite of the male genital segment as in Figs 3a, 3b. Aedeagus (Fig. 2; Fig. 3c) 1.37 mm long, ovoidal; inner sac with a broad, distal group of spinulae, followed by a short, median series of fine spines, between two lateral, long series of big spines, gradually longer; the proximal portion of the sac is folded on itself one time, covered with fine scales.

Etymology. The specific epithet refers to the type locality.

Distribution. The species is known from the type locality only.

Note. The new species belongs to the *rufipennis*-group (BORDONI, 2013). In the past I have described from Iran (BORDONI, 1983) another species (*X. martensi*) of the same group, very different by external characters and genitalia. The new species differs from the other species of this group especially for the punctation of pronotum and for the structure of the inner sac of the aedeagus. In particular it differs from *X. penicillatus* Assing, 2007 from Southwestern Turkey by colouration, punctation and by the placing and size of the spines on the inner sac of the aedeagus.

Xantholinus elegans (Olivier, 1795)

Examined material. Italy, Aosta Valley, Val Veni, leg. ? 14.VII.1972, 1 ex. (MCSNG); Liguria, Forte Diamante (GE), 1400 m, Franciscolo 13.XI.1979, 1 ex. (MCSNG); Umbria, Frontignano (PG), 1400 m, Battoni 7.IV.1969, 2 exx. (MCSNG); Colfiorito (PG), Battoni V.1969, 1 ex. (MCSNG).

Fig. 1. *Xantholinus chalusianus* sp. n.: habitus, scale bar: 1 mm (photo S. Cuoco).

Fig. 2. *Xantholinus chalusianus* sp. n.: aedeagus, scale bar: 0,2 mm (photo S. Cuoco).

Distribution. Central and East Europe, France, Italy, Greece (SMETANA, 2004). New record for Aosta Valley.

Xantholinus apennincola Steel, 1946

Examined material. Liguria, Torpiana, La Spezia, leg. ? XII.1984, 1 ex. (MCSNG); Sesta Godano (La Spezia), Casoni, 1000 m, leg. ? 9.VIII.1980, 1 ex. (MCSNG).

Distribution. Italy, Switzerland (SMETANA, 2004).

Xantholinus laniger Fauvel, 1899

Examined material. The Institut royal des Sciences naturelles of Bruxelles preserves 4 specimens, females, labelled “Djebel Taya/ grotte 3”, “Bou Berak/ près Dellys, Algerie”, “camp de la Santé, 3 (Tunisie)”, “El Fedja/ 12 (Tunisie)”. I chose the first as lectotype of the species and the others as paralectotypes. The first bears the label “Lectotypus *Xantholinus laniger* Fvl., Bordoni des. 2014”; the others bear the label “Paralectotypus *Xantholinus laniger* Fvl., Bordoni des. 2014”.

Distribution. Algeria, Tunisia (SMETANA, 2004). In the description of the species Fauvel (FAUVEL, 1899) cites Bona, Philippeville and Djebel Taya in Algeria and Teboursouk, Ain Draham and El Fedja in Tunisia.

Xantholinus gridellii Coiffait, 1856

Examined material. Jordan, 5 km NE El Karana, 31.58N, 35.36E, 200 m, S. Becvar 31.III.1994, 1 ♂ (cB); Jordan, Wadi El Hasa, 400 m, 30.58N, 35.47E, S. Becvar 6.IV.1994, 1 ♂ (cH).

Distribution. The species is known from Cyprus, Israel, Lebanon, Syria, Algeria (SMETANA, 2004). First record for Jordan.

***Xantholinus inuus* Fauvel, 1900**

Examined material. The Institut royal des Sciences naturelles of Bruxelles preserves 4 specimens. The first two bear the label “ex typis” (red printed on white label), one labelled “Teniet el Had/ Hauser”, with the label of Coiffait “Non. Le type est dans la coll. de Peyerimhoff. Il porte une étiquette “Type” de la main de Fauvel (?). C’est un ♂ des Gorges de la Chiffa (H. Coiffait 1.62)”; one is labelled “Gorges de la Chiffa, Alg.”. Waiting for be able to study the specimen, with the label of Coiffait, I refrain from designating a lectotype.

The others two specimens are from Algeria, Pic de Mouzaia, 1 ex. (IRSNB), 1 ex. (cB). I illustrated the genitalia of this species (Figs 3d, 3e, 3f).

Distribution. Algeria (SMETANA, 2004).

Note. In the description of the species FAUVEL (1900) cites Gorge de la Chiffa, Teniet-Had in Algeria (coll. Fauvel and Peyerimhoff).

Fig. 3. *Xantholinus chalusianus* sp. n.: a. tergite, b. sternite of the male genital segment; c. aedeagus. *Xantholinus inuus* Fauvel, 1900: d. tergite, e. sternite of the male genital segment; f. aedeagus; scale bar: 0.1 mm.

***Xantholinus fortepunctatus* Motschulsky, 1860**

Examined material. Iran, Binalut Geb., Shandiz, 2000 m, C. Blumenthal 3.VI.1974, 1 ♂ (NHMB).

Distribution. The species is known from some countries in Europe and Asia (SMETANA, 2004). This record confirms the presence of the species in Iran.

***Xantholinus caucasicus* Bordoni, 1975**

Examined material. E Caucasus, N Ossetie, Alagir, leg. ? 1.IX.1990, 1 ex. (cI), 1 ex. (cB).

Distribution. Turkey, Georgia, South Russia (SMETANA, 2004).

***Xantholinus sardous* Gridelli, 1947**

Examined material. Corsica, Vizzavona env., 1550 m, leg. ? 18.VII.1969, 1 ex.; ile Rousse, leg. ? 20.VII.1972, 1 ex. (MCSNG).

Distribution. Corsica, Sardinia, Majorca, Algeria, Morocco (BORDONI, 1982; SMETANA, 2004).

***Xantholinus cerrutti* Coiffait, 1964**

Examined material. Italy, Abruzzo, Maielletta, Blockhaus, Canepari 7.VII.1981, 1 ♂ (cC); Gran Sasso, Campo Imperatore, leg. ? 8-12.VI.1972, 3 exx (MCSNG); idem, 15.VI.1988, 1 ex. (MCSNG).

Distribution. Endemic species of South and Central Apennines (BORDONI, 1982).

***Xantholinus maritimus* Reitter, 1908**

Examined material. Italy, Liguria, Chiavari env. (GE), 1200 m, leg. ? 11.V.1961, 1 ex. (MCSNG); Mt Gottero, La Spezia, 1500-1550 m, 1-23.IX.1979, 3 exx. (MCSNG), 1 ex. (cB); Passo del Melogno (SV), leg. ? VI.1959, 1 ex. (MCSNG).

Distribution. Mountain species of French and Italian Maritime Alps, Cottian Alps and Apennines of Liguria, Tuscany, and Abruzzo (BORDONI, 1982). The new records expand the distribution in Liguria.

***Xantholinus kirghisicus* Coiffait, 1966**

Examined material. SW Kirgiza, Chathal H., 3400 m, Aflatun riv., leg. ? 2.VIII.1998, 1 ♂ (cB).

Distribution. Kyrgyzstan (SMETANA, 2004).

***Milichilinus decorus* (Erichson, 1839)**

Examined material. Slovakia, Small Carpatians Mts, Smolenice, castle, 500 m, A. Barsevskis 25-30.III.2007, 2 exx. (ISBD), 1 ex. (cB).

Distribution. East Europe (SMETANA, 2004).

***Allolinus insolens* Smetana, 1967**

Examined material. Mongolia, Terelji, T. Ito 7-10.VII.1996, 1 ♂, 1 ♀ (cI), 1 ♂ (cB).

Distribution. Mongolia (SMETANA, 2004).

Phacophallus flavipennis (Kraatz, 1859)

Examined material. Pakistan, Karachi, E. Heiss 11-4.VII.1971, 2 exx. (MM), 1 ex. (cB).

Distribution. Indian, Indochinese and Indo-Malay subregions (BORDONI, 2002). New record for Pakistan. According to my conclusions in the revision of the Oriental Xantholinini (BORDONI, 2002), the part of Pakistan West of Indo river belongs to the Palaearctic Region.

Megalinus glabratus (Gravenhorst, 1802)

Examined material. NE Morocco, Beni-Snassen Mts, Taforalt, 34.49N, 2.24W, 800 m, Kalab 1.XI.2002, 3 exx. (cC), 2 exx. (cB).

Distribution. Widespread species in Europe and Mediterranean area (SMETANA, 2004).

Megalinus pseudohesperius (Reitter, 1908)

Examined material. Italy, Sicily, Strada Gela-Caltagirone, leg. ? 2.XII.1972, 1 ♂ (cC).

Distribution. Sicily, Sardinia, Portugal, Spain, North Africa (SMETANA, 2004).

Medhiana pauper (Sharp, 1889)

Examined material. Russian Far East, Kurilian Isl., Kanashir Isl., leg. ? 20-30.VII.1997, 2 exx. (cI), 1 ex. (cB).

Distribution. Japan, South China, North India (Himachal Pradesh), Nepal (BORDONI, 2002); Kurili Isl. (SHIBATA *et al.*, 2006).

Furthermore the following nomenclature act is made: *Xantholinus postfactus* nom. nov. for *Xantholinus apterus* Bordoni, 2016, nom preocc. by *Xantholinus apterus* Bernhauer, 1939.

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